

Heterobimetallic mixed metal oxide (HMMO) nanoparticles and their applications[†]

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The chemistry of HMMO (heterobimetallic mixed metal oxide) nanoparticles of the type ABO_3 (perovskite), AB_2O_4 (spinel and antispinel) and AB_2O_5 (pseudobrookite) has been discussed. Their preparation by the sol-gel route using mixtures of alkoxides, heterobimetallic alkoxides and heterobimetallic- μ -oxo alkoxides are described. Physical and chemical properties, with special reference to high surface area, morphology, crystal structure, catalysis and destructive adsorption studies, along with some important applications have also been discussed.

Developments in the field of HMMO nanoparticles have produced very significant and interesting results, which are evident from the recent reports published¹⁻⁵ in the literature. HMMO nanoparticles exhibit a wide array of unusual properties and can be considered as new materials that bridge molecular and condensed matter. One of the unusual features is their enhanced surface chemical reactivity towards incoming adsorbates⁶⁻⁸ and chemical warfare agents^{9,10}. For example, Al_2O_3/MgO HMMO nanoparticles adsorb⁸ SO_2 and CCl_4 , and $MgAl_2O_4$ adsorbs and destroys paraxon [diethyl-4-nitrophenol phosphate (DNPP)]¹¹ more efficiently as compared to commercially prepared and pure MgO and Al_2O_3 nanoparticles. This enhanced surface reactivity is attributed to the presence of high concentration of edge/corner sites and other defects, which makes HMMO nanoparticles co-ordinatively unsaturated. Furthermore, the presence of two different metal centres in HMMOs increases their efficiency, due to the close proximity of acidic and basic centres.

In short, the following factors are considered to be important for the unusual chemical properties of HMMO nanoparticles : (i) acid-base behaviour, (ii) high surface area (due to the small particle size with dimensions in the range 1-10 nm), (iii) several types of deficiencies in the bulk as well as on the surface. The above stated properties make these HMMO nanoparticles the best candidates for catalysis¹²⁻¹⁸ (both as catalysts and catalytic supports) and destructive adsorption⁶⁻⁸.

HMMO nanoparticle systems have been given special attention because of their unique size dependent properties, such as optical, electronic, and magnetic, in comparison to

normal HMMOs. Semimagnetic semiconductors of nanometer-sized crystallites are expected to be influenced by the quantum confinement of the electronic states and have great potential for a variety of applications due to the unique properties of quantum dots³.

The synthesis of HMMO nanoparticles by the conventional method is based on solid-state reaction¹⁹, which requires repeated cycles of milling and calcination at high temperature. This results in lack of homogeneity (due to incomplete reaction) and low surface area ($\sim 1 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$). In contrast to the solid-state method, various other physical and chemical methods are preferred. Physical methods include gas condensation techniques²⁰⁻²², spray pyrolysis^{23,24}, thermochemical decomposition of metal-organic precursors in flame reactors²⁵, and some other aerosol processes named according to the energy sources applied to reach the required temperatures during gas-particle conversion. The wet chemical methods include the sol-gel method, reverse micro emulsion technique²⁶⁻²⁸ and precipitation from solution^{29,30}. It has been observed that, out of the various physical and chemical methods, the sol-gel method assumes special significance for the preparation of more homogeneous nanosized HMMOs of high purity and surface area.

A survey of the literature shows that sol-gel³¹⁻³⁷ processing has several advantages over other techniques for synthesizing nanopowders of mixed metal oxide ceramics. These include (i) the production of ultrafine porous powders, (ii) the homogeneity of the product as a result of homogeneous mixing of the starting materials at the molecular level and (iii) the possibility of obtaining the ceramic material in different forms by controlling the conditions. In

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this process, a colloidal sol is converted into a gel by ageing. The gel is subsequently calcined by special techniques, giving rise to a crystalline product with homogeneous composition and large surface area.

In view of the solubility of metal alkoxides^{38–40} and oxo-alkoxides^{41,42} in organic solvents, these materials are strongly preferred as precursors in sol-gel processes. In heterobimetallic- μ -oxo alkoxides, M–O–M' linkage is present, which makes the M–O–M' bond strong and stable as compared to other precursors. Non-cleavage of the M–O–M' bond, even upon hydrolysis followed by dehydration (drying), makes homogeneous oxides of high surface area HMMO nanoparticles. Interestingly, the structural relationship among these precursors, coupled with their versatility towards hydrolysis, led to their increasing use as starting compounds. These compounds are considered as especially suitable precursors over other precursors such as metal nitrates, acetates, monodispersed metal hydrous oxides, mainly due to the ease of their purification (either by distillation or recrystallization), solubility in organic solvents, and their extremely facile hydrolyzability.

This article describes the synthesis of HMMO nanoparticles (perovskite, spinel and pseudobrookite) using either mixtures of metal alkoxides, heterobimetallic alkoxides or heterobimetallic- μ -oxo alkoxides as precursors by the sol-gel method. Other methods of the preparation, and composite/doped nanoparticles are not being covered.

The sol-gel route can be considered as a two-step inorganic polymerization.

(i) *Hydrolysis of metal alkoxides* : In this step, polymerization starts by hydrolysis at the metal-alkoxy linkage yielding alcohol and a new reactant containing hydroxylated metal centres (M–OH).

(ii) *Condensation* : In this step, three-dimensional propagation occurs when hydroxylated species condense to form oxypolymers by the combination of the following steps.

The nature of the inorganic framework depends upon the relative rates of hydrolysis and condensation at different centres. The rate of hydrolysis depends upon the nature of the metal in terms of its electrophilicity and ability to expand its co-ordination number⁴³. The hydrolysis rates of transition metal alkoxides (especially in the case of

heterobimetallic alkoxides) are very high due to their highly electrophilic nature and ability to expand their coordination number. This sometimes complicates the problem by causing phase segregation and, to overcome this problem, a modified precursor is prepared by reacting the alkoxide with other ligands. This results in a new precursor, which may undergo hydrolysis at a slower rate⁴⁴. Finally, the solvent is removed from the gel. The manner in which the liquid phase is removed from the wet gel determines whether the dried material is a highly porous aerogel or a denser xerogel. Xerogel is formed as the solvent from wet gel evaporates resulting in a collapse of the wet gel structure. In case the network is compliant, the gel deforms due to the capillary forces generated by the liquid phase as it recedes into the body of the gel. Aerogel is actually a nanoscale mesoporous material of low density and high surface area, which results from supercritical drying (SCD)^{45,46} or ambient pressure methods upon wet gels.

Structure and morphology of HMMO nanoparticles

HMMO nanoparticles are known to have different structure and morphology, depending upon the size and charge of the constituent ions. The nature of these ions determines the final geometry adopted. HMMO nanoparticles prepared by the sol-gel method most often adopt one of the perovskite, spinel and pseudobrookite types of structures.

Perovskite structure (ABO₃ type)

HMMOs having the formula ABO₃ are called perovskite, e.g., CaTiO₃⁴⁷, SrTiO₃⁴⁸, BaTiO₃⁴⁸, etc. HMMOs of the type SrTiO₃ and BaTiO₃ have been prepared by reacting both the alkoxides in a 1 : 1 molar ratio by the sol-gel method, shown in Scheme 1. CaTiO₃ has been prepared⁴⁷ from calcium acetate and titanium isopropoxide in 1 : 1 molar ratio and calcinations of the gel powder in air at temperatures upto 900°.

Recently, translucent BaTiO₃⁴⁹ and GdFeO₃⁵⁰ have been prepared by the sol-gel method using metal alkoxides in 1 : 1 molar ratio, followed by calcination at higher temperature (600–1100°).

The XRD pattern (Fig. 1) of SrTiO₃ in different solvents shows that it is an amorphous powder in ethanol. Furthermore, comparison of the XRD patterns of HMMO perovskites of the type SrTiO₃, BaTiO₃ and CaTiO₃, after calcination at different temperatures, suggests that calcination at 500° under pressure for SrTiO₃ and BaTiO₃, and at 900° in air for CaTiO₃, results in the appearance of an intense peak, indicative of high surface/volume ratio.

Scheme 1. Preparation route of perovskite SrTiO₃ or BaTiO₃.

Surface area analyses of these perovskites are given in Tables 1–3, which suggest that HMMO perovskites prepared by the sol-gel process have high surface area as compared to commercially available samples.

Fig. 1. XRD patterns for synthesis of SrTiO₃ with different alcohols.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) micrograph⁴⁸ of SrTiO₃ (Fig. 2) indicates that it has a crystallite size of 10 nm, when calcined at 500°.

HMMO	S.A. of HMMO prepd. by S-G (m ² /g ⁻¹)	Commercial HMMO (m ² /g ⁻¹)
CaTiO ₃	21	–
SrTiO ₃	159	17
BaTiO ₃	175	20–30

Table 2. Aerogel SrTiO₃ (ethanol calcined) at different temperatures

Conditions °C	Crystallite sizes, nm	Surface area m ² /g ⁻¹	Pore volume, cc/g	Average pore size, Å
200	8	159	0.617	155
300	6	156	0.571	145
400	9	114	0.544	190
500	10	93	0.453	194

Table 3. Aerogel BaTiO₃ (ethanol isopropanol) at different temperatures

Conditions °C	Surface area m ² /g ⁻¹	Total pore volume, cc/g	Avg pore size (d), Å
300	175	0.434	101.7
400	89	0.368	165
500	45	0.391	345.7

The structure of the perovskite phase was first thought to be cubic, but later confirmed as orthorhombic. The truly cubic form is referred to as "ideal perovskite", having a unit cell edge of ~4 Å containing one ABO₃. In this phase, the large cation A is surrounded by 12 oxide ions to form cuboctahedral co-ordination, whereas the B cation is surrounded by 6 oxide ions in an octahedral co-ordination.

Fig. 2. TEM of SrTiO₃ aerogel calcined at 500°.

The combination of high surface areas and nanosizes of aerogel SrTiO₃ and BaTiO₃ mixed oxides gives significant advantages in different applications, which are currently being explored.

Spinel structure (AB₂O₄ type)

It consists of a face-centered cubic arrangement of oxygen ions. A unit cell contains 32 O²⁻ ions, 64 tetrahedral and 32 octahedral sites, which are occupied by A²⁺ (A = Mg, Fe, Ca, Zn, etc.) and B³⁺ (B = Al, Fe, etc.) cations, respectively. The general formula of the spinel is written as

$A^{II}B^{III}_2O_4$ [where A^{II} is a group 2 metal ion or transition metal in the +2 oxidation state and B^{III} is a Group 13 (B, Al, Ga, In) cation or transition metal ion in the +3 oxidation state]. $MgAl_2O_4$, $CaAl_2O_4$, $MnAl_2O_4$, $FeAl_2O_4$, $CoAl_2O_4$, $NiAl_2O_4$, $ZnAl_2O_4$, etc., were successfully prepared by Kapoor *et al.*⁵¹. Recently, $ZnAl_2O_4$ has also been prepared⁵² from the heterobimetallic alkoxide via the sol-gel method followed by calcination at 400°. This is a very stable type of HMMO, prepared by the sol-gel technique shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2. Preparation route of spinel $MgAl_2O_4$.

The XRD pattern (Fig. 3a) of $MgAl_2O_4$ shows that it is spinel at $\sim 500^\circ$, but on increasing the temperature, the intensity of the peak increases, which suggests that the size of the particle decreases. Furthermore, the XRD patterns (Fig. 3b) for MAI_2O_4 (where $M = Fe, Co, Zn$) were examined by Kapoor *et al.*⁵¹, and compared with the XRD pattern of

Fig. 3(a). XRD of $MgAl_2O_4$.

Fig. 3(b). XRD of $ZnAl_2O_4$: (a) as synthesized and (b) after heat treatment at 500° for 1 h.

$MgAl_2O_4$, which shows superimposability, suggesting their spinel structure.

Surface area⁵¹ analyses (Table 4) show that $Mg-O-Al$, prepared by the oxo bridge method has the highest surface area upto $440 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and $470 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ after heat treatment at 500° in vacuum. However, $Mg-O-Al$, when prepared by the bridged alkoxide method, shows surface areas of only $228 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and $242 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ after heat treatment. These results reflect the advantages of the method utilizing the oxo-bridged precursors to obtain high surface area homogeneous HMMO nanoparticles. Analogous $Zn-O-Al$, $Fe-O-Al$, $Co-O-Al$ and $Mn-O-Al$ surface areas were in the range of $310\text{--}340 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. TEM studies (Fig. 4) of spinels suggest their crystallite sizes.

MAI_2O_4	S.A. ($\text{m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) after SCD	S.A. ($\text{m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) after heat treatment at 500° under vacuum
$M = Mg$	228	242
$M = Ca$	260	155
$M = Zn$	320	340
$M = Co$	330	315
$M = Fe$	320	310
$M = Mn$	320	308

Solid state ^{27}Al NMR (Fig. 5 and Table 5) is a good tool for analyzing the co-ordination environment of Al^{3+} ions, in particular the octahedral to tetrahedral ratio, and their existence. When A^{2+} ions occupy one eighth of the tetrahedral holes and B^{3+} ions half the octahedral holes, the structure is called "normal" spinel. It is a stable arrangement having tetrahedral arrangement about a divalent cat-

Fig. 4. (a) TEM micrograph of the ZnAl₂O₄ material, after 500° heat treatment under vacuum, (b) high resolution TEM with SAD pattern shown in the inset.

Fig. 5. ²⁷Al NMR of MAI₂O₄ : (a) CaAl₂O₄, (b) MgAl₂O₄, (c) ZnAl₂O₄, (d) MgAl₂O₄(Mg-OR-Al).

Table 5. ²⁷Al solid-state MAS NMR spectra

Sample	Peak position (δ)		Oh : Td ratio
	Oh	Td	
MgAl ₂ O ₄	9.7	70	74 : 26
ZnAl ₂ O ₄	9.7	66	85 : 15
CaAl ₂ O ₄	8.7	70	47 : 53

ion and octahedral arrangement about a trivalent cation.

In some cases, e.g. NiFe₂O₄, one half of the B³⁺ ions exchange their positions with A²⁺ ions. This is called "inverse" spinel. In this arrangement, one eighth of tetrahedral

sites are occupied by half of the B³⁺ ions, whereas the rest of the B³⁺ ions, along with the A²⁺ ions, occupy half of the octahedral sites. The general formula for "normal" spinel is written as (A)[B]₂O₄, while for "inverse" spinel, it is (B)[AB]O₄, where () and [] represent tetrahedral and octahedral arrangements. Many MMOs have intermediate cation ratios, and the general formula of these structures is written as (A_{1-x}B_x)[B_{2-x}A_x]O₄, where x is the "inversion parameter" (0 < x < 1).

Pseudobrookite structure (AB₂O₅ type)

HMMOs of this type have the general formula AB₂O₅. Pseudobrookite is a rare oxide mineral and provides this type of structure for a variety of minerals and synthetic phases. The mineral name derives from its appearance. Pseudobrookite resembles brookite, one of the titanium dioxide polymorphs. The synthetic phase "Karooite" MgTi₂O₅ also has the pseudobrookite structure in which both the metal ions are co-ordinated by six oxygens, e.g., MgTi₂O₅⁵³, FeTi₂O₅⁵⁴, etc.

All these pseudobrookite phases are metastable at RT. Stability at high temperature has been proposed to result from the mixing of cations between two different cation-oxygen octahedra, which are connected by shared edges.

This phase (MTi₂O₅) is readily converted into rutile or anatase TiO₂, and perovskite structure MTiO₃. Only few HMMOs of this class are known; other pseudobrookites such as AB₂O₅ (M = Ca, Mn, Zn; M' = Ti)⁵⁵ have been prepared and further studies are going on.

MgTi₂O₅ has been successfully prepared⁵⁵ by the sol-gel method, which is shown in Scheme 3. Comparison of the XRD pattern (Fig. 6) for MgTi₂O₅ prepared⁵⁵ by the

Scheme 3. Preparation route of pseudobrookite MgTi₂O₅.

sol-gel process with that of MgTi_2O_5 prepared by heating MgO and TiO_2 high temperature in a 1 : 2 molar ratio, exhibits superimposable pattern, showing their similar structures.

Fig. 6. XRD pattern of MgTi_2O_5 .

Properties and applications

The properties of HMMO nanoparticles are size dependent. They exhibit unique chemical and physical properties that are remarkably different from those of the corresponding bulk materials. As the particle size decreases, the percentage of atoms residing on the surface increases, giving high surface to volume ratios. This allows more reactive centres becoming available for reactions to occur.

A variety of important aspects centre around the unusual chemical properties of HMMO nanoparticles; some of these are described below :

(1) As destructive adsorbents :

The development of novel methods for the disposal of chlorinated wastes and other toxic gases in the environment, from industries as well as other sources, has become a very urgent task. Recent studies have shown that HMMO nanoparticles attract significant attention as effective chemisorbents for such toxic gases as well as chlorine and phosphorus containing compounds.

For this purpose, HMMOs play an important role. For example, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{MgO}$ adsorbs⁸ SO_2 , CCl_4 and paraxon more efficiently as compared to pure Al_2O_3 and MgO nanoparticles and commercially available oxides.

Adsorption of SO_2 was carried out with pure MgO , Al_2O_3 and mixed oxide $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{MgO}$ and compared. The experimental results showed that, at atmospheric pressure and RT, the SO_2 adsorbed onto Al_2O_3 nanoparticles was 3.5 molecules of SO_2/nm^2 , on MgO nanoparticles it was 0.68 molecules of SO_2/nm^2 , but the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{MgO}$ MMO nanoparticles layer adsorbed 6.8 molecules of SO_2/nm^2 .

These data indicate that $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{MgO}$ efficiently adsorbs SO_2 in slightly more than one layer. This is probably due to the greater Lewis basicity of the MgO present and large surface area of Al_2O_3 , which is beneficial for the adsorption of the acid gas.

In the last few decades, pollution by diesel-engine exhausts has become an ever-increasingly serious problem. Soot and NO_x are the main components to be removed from diesel exhaust. Among bimetallic spinel type oxides, CuFe_2O_4 may be useful, which shows intermediate activity and exceptionally high and low selectivity, respectively, to N_2 and N_2O formation⁵⁶.

The most interesting application of HMMO spinels is for adsorbing paraxon¹¹. These particles possess their destructive adsorption ability due to the presence of acidic and basic oxides in one intermingled mixed metal oxide. HMMO nanoparticles, such as MAl_2O_4 ($\text{M} = \text{Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba}$) have been used for this purpose. To compare the relative adsorption efficiencies of various MMOs, 16 μL of paraxon and 100 mg of adsorbent were used. The results (Figs. 7 and 8) show that both MgAl_2O_4 and CaAl_2O_4 destructively adsorbed all 8 μL , whereas SrAl_2O_4 and BaAl_2O_4 were only able to destructively adsorb 6 μL before their surface became saturated. Therefore, HMMO systems of MgAl_2O_4 and CaAl_2O_4 are better at destructively adsorbing paraxon than SrAl_2O_4 , BaAl_2O_4 , pure MgO , CaO and Al_2O_3 nanoparticles. Another HMMO nanoparticle, SrTiO_3 is photoactive⁴⁸ under UV light and is able to decompose organic volatile compounds like acetaldehyde.

Fig. 7. Reaction of AP- MgAl_2O_4 with paraxon (16 μl) after 20 min.

(2) In catalysis :

Relatively little work has been reported where these nanostructured materials have been explored in classical catalytic processes. Some examples are given below.

Fig. 8. Reaction of AP-CaAl₂O₄ with paraxon (16 μ l) after 40 min.

In CuMn₂O₄, the Cu-Mn-O system is a well-known oxidation catalyst⁵⁷ for carbon monoxide oxidation with oxygen at RT. The activity of CuMn₂O₄ decreases at temperatures above 600° due to the crystallization of spinel CuMn₂O₄. The high activity of CuMn₂O₄ is believed to be due to the redox system $\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{Mn}^{3+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}^{+} + \text{Mn}^{4+}$ and unique adsorption properties of carbon monoxide on Cu²⁺/Mn⁴⁺ as well as O₂ on Cu⁺/Mn³⁺. Similarly, NiMn₂O₄ and CuCo₂O₄ also have high activity.

It is clear that surface properties such as the precise surface structures and the role of point defects are crucial to the proper understanding of the catalytic⁵⁶ and electrochemical properties. La₂NiO₄ has been widely studied for its catalytic properties such as partial oxidation and hypochlorite decomposition. There is continuing interest in La₂CuO₄ since it also exhibits catalytic properties. It is used in several chemical reactions^{59–61} including CO oxidation, NO reduction, CH₄ oxidation and as a three-way automobile exhaust catalyst⁶¹.

Besides these applications, MA₂O₄ (Ca, Sr, Ba)⁶² have been widely used as hosts for ceramic pigments, practical phosphors and excitation sources for other phosphors and luminous paints.

Recently, Co-Ti pseudobrookite (uncalcined) oxide nanoparticles⁵⁵ were found to be good photocatalysts for the decomposition of acetaldehyde to carbon dioxide.

(3) In electronics, magnetics and optics :

HMMO nanoparticles are characterized by an ultrafine grain size (<50 nm). These particles are subjects of current interest because of their unusual magnetic, optical and electronic properties, which often differ from their bulk properties. The reasons for these are the confinement of electronic and vibrational excitation, quantum size effect and large sur-

face to volume ratio. Perovskite type oxides of the general formula ABO₃ are important in materials science, physics and earth sciences, e.g., for their electrical properties. These are widely used for the preparation of electronic components, electro-optical and photocatalytic materials. For example, SrTiO₃, BaTiO₃ and related compounds have been extensively used in the preparation of high dielectric constant capacitors, PTC resistors, transducers and ferroelectric memories.

LaGeO₃ and La₂NiO₄ are of current interest due to their potential applications in solid oxide fuel cells and ceramic membranes for oxygen separation. The LiM₂O₄ type of spinels is also important. LiTi₂O₄ was the first oxide superconductor with a transition temperature exceeding 10 K. LiV₂O₄ showed all the characteristics of a heavy fermion system with an effective mass enhancement of the order of 100. Similarly, LiMn₂O₄ a very important positive electrode material for commercial Li-ion batteries.

ZnFe₂O₄ is well known as an anomalous antiferromagnetic substance. Recent studies have shown that ZnFe₂O₄, especially nanometer-sized nanoparticles, with a relatively small band gap, is a potentially useful solar energy material for photoelectric conversion and photochemical hydrogen production from water⁶³. It has the advantage of absorbing visible light, without being sensitive to photoanodic corrosion.

Conclusion

The above brief account clearly depicts a versatile fast developing chemistry of HMMO nanoparticles, which is many a time being triggered by the multifaceted demands for advanced oxide-ceramics with novel applications. These HMMOs, prepared by the sol-gel process, are nanoparticles of ultrafine purity and high surface area. This high surface area is responsible for their applications in destructive adsorption, catalysis, and other applications, such as in magnetics, optics and electronics.

Besides the above applications, metal oxide nanoparticles have either been used or tested for their applications in the following fields :

(1) *Decontamination of chemical warfare agents (CWAs)*: CWAs are generally organophosphorus esters. e.g., nerve agents (also called "Soman") and blister agents (also called "mustard"). Nerve agents can react with the enzyme acetylcholinesterase, which inhibits its control over the central nervous system. Reaction of the CWAs on MgO, CaO or Al₂O₃ nanoparticles at RT decontaminates¹⁰ them by the cleavage of the P-O and P-F bonds and make them non-toxic.

(2) *Biocidal activity* : Some nanomaterials possess biocidal activity^{64,65} towards spores and vegetative cells, viruses and toxins. For this purpose, CaO and MgO nanoparticles are generally used. MgO nanoparticles adsorb chlorine to form deep yellow adduct MgO.Cl₂ nanoparticles. This adduct is capable of oxidizing bacteria. This killing action is not well understood, but may be due to a combination of the abrasive nature of the MgO nanoparticles and oxidizing ability of the surface chlorine.

(3) *Cosmetics* : TiO₂ and ZnO nanoparticles have been used in sunscreen creams for protection against UV irradiation.

(4) *Pharmaceuticals* : They are also used as drug delivery agents. Nanoparticles have been developed that can safely cross the blood-brain barrier and deliver therapeutic agents to particular parts of the brain. Silica coated semiconductor nanoparticles are readily incorporated into a wide variety of eukaryotic cells.

(5) *Nanotechnology* : It is the science of building machines and materials at the molecular level, where key components are measured in nanometers. This promises medical advances, smarter and lighter materials, more efficient manufacturing, cleaner energy, faster and more efficient electronics and better ways to detect, prevent and treat pollution.

In light of the extensive studies and probable applications of HMMOs, they may prove to be the materials of this century.

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